

Assertiveness in Learning and Academic Attitude of Pupils in Asuncion, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the influence of assertiveness in learning on the academic attitude of learners. In this study, the researcher selected the 168 Grade 6 learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that assertiveness in learning and academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between assertiveness in learning and the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. Evidently, regression analysis proved that assertiveness in learning in terms of passive behavior and aggressive behavior significantly influenced the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. DepEd should develop and implement policies that promote a supportive and inclusive school culture. Encourage policies that discourage bullying, discrimination, and other behaviors that may hinder the development of assertiveness in learners.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management 2. academic attitude of learners 3. assertiveness
in learning

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1. Introduction

Learners' attitudes toward their academic pursuits play a crucial role in shaping their educational experiences and outcomes. A positive academic attitude fosters engagement, motivation, and active participation, which are essential for effective learning. Conversely, a negative academic attitude can have detrimental effects, leading to disengagement, reduced participation, and a decline in overall classroom dynamics. Such attitudes not only hinder individual students' academic progress but also affect the collective learning environment, limiting opportunities for collaboration and the exchange of ideas. Addressing these issues necessitates a comprehensive approach that involves educators, parents, and the community, aimed at fostering a supportive and motivating atmosphere. Central to this effort is understanding the role of assertiveness in learning, on how students' confidence and ability to express themselves influ-

ence their academic attitudes. This study examines the relationship between assertiveness and pupils' academic attitudes in Asuncion, Davao Del Norte, to identify strategies to promote a more positive and proactive learning environment. Globally, as reported by Mallilin (2020), learners with a negative academic attitude often experience a decline in academic performance. They may be less motivated to complete assignments, study for exams, and actively engage in the learning process, resulting in lower grades. A consistently negative attitude toward learning may limit students' interest in pursuing advanced courses or extracurricular activities. This restriction can impact their exposure to diverse educational experiences and opportunities. Adding more, Sahin and Yilmaz (2020) reported that a negative academic attitude often leads to decreased interest in attending school. Students may view school as a burden, and this lack of enthusiasm can contribute to absenteeism, disengagement, and a reluctance to participate in classroom activities. By contrast, Xie et al. (2022) noted that students with a moderate academic attitude exhibit balanced motivation. They are motivated to succeed but not overly stressed, allowing for a healthy level of drive to excel in their studies. They engage in learning activities with enthusiasm that supports their academic goals. They actively participate in class, complete assignments, and seek additional resources to deepen their understanding. According to Assem et al. (2023), at the national level, learners with a positive academic attitude set realistic educational goals and work steadily toward achieving them. Their goals are attainable and aligned with their capabilities. They manage academic stressors in a healthy, constructive manner. Likewise, Agormedah et al. (2021) pointed out that learners with moderate academic attitudes practice effective time management. They allocate sufficient time to studying, attending classes, and participating in extracurricular activities, thereby maintaining

a balanced lifestyle. Meanwhile, studies have indicated that assertiveness in learning is associated with learners' academic attitudes. For instance, Waqar and Sanjay (2022) found that assertive learners are more likely to actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, and express their opinions. This engagement enhances their understanding of the material and demonstrates a proactive attitude toward learning. In the Philippine setting, growing attention has been given to the role of academic attitudes in shaping student outcomes. A study in Zamboanga Sibugay revealed that motivation and attitude toward Social Studies are crucial to learners' progress (Benitez, 2022). Pupils who showed interest and enthusiasm performed better and absorbed lessons faster compared to peers with weaker motivation (Tolentino et al., 2023). In other Philippine contexts, the link between attitude and performance is further demonstrated in language learning. Among elementary students in Misamis Occidental, a study examined the affective, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions of pupils' attitudes toward English and found that these dimensions significantly influenced academic outcomes (Seraspe, 2022). A related study among students discovered that a strong sense of self-worth predicted positive learning attitudes (Baria Gomez, 2022). Specifically, the identity achievement and identity moratorium dimensions have been shown to foster more favorable approaches to school tasks, highlighting the impact of self-concept on academic outlook (Datu et al., 2022). Overall, national evidence affirms that students' academic attitudes, whether directed toward specific subjects, learning environments, or self-perceptions, play a vital role in shaping their participation and performance. Pupils who display positive attitudes are more motivated, exert greater effort, and engage more actively in lessons, while negative dispositions often hinder persistence and self-confidence (Sabanal, 2023). These findings suggest that schools should inte-

grate teaching strategies, learning activities, and supportive interventions designed to strengthen positive academic attitudes, ensuring that Filipino learners remain motivated and resilient across grade levels and subject areas, regardless of changing educational contexts or delivery modes (Valdez et al., 2022). In Davao del Norte, research on learners' behavior and academic outlook remains limited, revealing a significant gap in understanding how local educational practices influence students' attitudes, particularly in communities such as Asuncion. While existing studies indicate that peer collaboration and teacher support foster active participation and confidence, there is a need for focused investigation into how initiatives such as guidance interventions and literacy programs impact students' assertiveness and overall academic attitudes. Addressing this gap is crucial, as understanding these dynamics can lead to the development of targeted, community-specific strategies to enhance educational outcomes. The social value of this research, titled "Assertiveness in Learning and Academic Attitude of Pupils in Asuncion, Davao del Norte," lies in its potential to inform the creation of effective, community-driven educational programs that promote confident, proactive learners. By identifying the factors influencing assertive learning behaviors, stakeholders, including educators, policymakers, and community leaders, can implement tailored interventions that foster supportive learning environments, ultimately improving academic performance and motivating lifelong learning among pupils in the area.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study —The study is anchored in Jakubowski-Spector's (1977, as cited in Hollandsworth Wall, 1977) Theory of Assertion, which rests on the premise that every individual possesses certain basic human rights. These rights include such fundamentals as the right to refuse requests without having to feel guilty

or selfish, the right to have one's own needs be as important as the needs of other people, the right to make mistakes, and the right to express ourselves as long as we do not violate the rights of others. Assertiveness helps learners address conflicts constructively. Instead of avoiding or escalating conflicts, assertive individuals seek resolutions that benefit all parties, thereby maintaining a positive academic environment. Also, the study is anchored on the proposition of Waqar and Sanjay (2022) that assertive learners are more likely to actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, and express their opinions. This engagement enhances their understanding of the material and demonstrates a proactive attitude toward learning. Assertiveness involves expressing thoughts and ideas clearly and confidently. Assertive learners are better equipped to communicate with peers and instructors, leading to more effective collaboration and a positive academic environment. They are adept at advocating for their own needs. Whether seeking clarification on assignments, discussing accommodations, or expressing concerns, assertiveness enables learners to take control of their educational experience. According to Blegur et al. (2023), assertive learners are more likely to prioritize their academic responsibilities. They proactively manage their time, set goals, and take the necessary steps to meet deadlines, leading to a more positive and organized academic attitude. Likewise, Keates (2022) found that assertive learners are receptive to and provide constructive feedback. They view feedback as a tool for improvement rather than as criticism, contributing to a growth mindset and a positive attitude toward academic development. As shown in Figure 1, the study involved two key variables. The independent variable was assertiveness in learning, which was described as the participants' ability to express their opinions, needs, and feelings in a direct, honest, and appropriate way. This variable was considered crucial

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

for understanding how assertiveness influenced learning outcomes. Additionally, the study explored how varying levels of assertiveness impacted students' participation, confidence, and overall academic performance, providing insights into the role of assertiveness in educational settings. According to Waqar and Sanjay (2022) assertiveness in learning is measured in terms of passive behavior or the behavior of individual manifesting insecurity when interacting with others in speaking and in their constant search to please the people around them regardless of their own good; aggressive behavior or the natural reaction of an individual to an event internally and externally that triggers an emotional feeling which results in aggressive behavior being demonstrated; manipulation or

the behavior that a person uses to gain power over another that include attempts to damage another person's well-being; and harmonious assertiveness or being honest about one's agenda while accepting contradiction. The dependent variable is learners' academic attitudes, defined as the process by which learners significantly affect learning. The measure of academic attitude of pupils according to June and Eamoraphan (2019) are academic self-concept or the factor that concerns the student's perceptions of his or her capability to master the subject matter and to do well; enjoyment or the extent to which the student enjoys the classes and the subject matter itself; and perceived value or the beliefs that the students hold about the importance of the subject in every day and in later life.

2. Methodology

This section details the research design, respondents, instruments, data-gathering procedures, and data-analysis methods. It outlines how the study systematically examines pupils' assertiveness and academic attitudes in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, ensuring reliable and valid results. The respondents include pupils, teachers, and administrators, providing diverse perspectives. Data collection involves the use of validated questionnaires and interviews, with appropriate ethical

safeguards in place. Data analysis employs appropriate statistical and qualitative techniques to interpret findings and inform targeted educational strategies.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to collect data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is grounded in a deductive approach that emphasizes testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, whereas non-experimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Creswell (2013, as cited in Mohajan, 2020), is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables without seeking to establish causal connections. In this study, the researcher examined the assertiveness in learning and academic attitudes of pupils in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. Specifically, the study focused on the relationships among variables to determine the significance of the relationship between the two variables. In this study, a descriptive-correlational design was appropriate because the researcher focused solely on the respondents' behavioral aspects and did not conduct an experiment in a controlled setting.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires, along with supporting author statements, were submitted for further evaluation. After obtaining Ethics Committee approval, the researcher proceeded to the next

phase of the study.

Informed Consent

In relation to the study on assertiveness in learning and academic attitudes of pupils in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, the researcher secured written informed consent from all participants. The respondents were thoroughly informed about the study's objectives and received detailed explanations to ensure they understood the purpose of their involvement. They were made aware that participation was entirely voluntary, with no pressure to participate, and that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. The researcher prioritized the respondents' psychological well-being and assured confidentiality. Each participant provided written consent, acknowledging that the study aimed to identify factors influencing learners' academic attitudes and assertiveness, with the goal of contributing to educational improvements.

Vulnerability of Research Participants

The study respondents are pupils, who are considered vulnerable because not all are of legal age and are highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Additionally, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the disclosed information.

Privacy and Confidentiality

This study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, under which the researcher ensured that data could not be traced back to participants, the primary source of information, to protect respondents' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without participants' consent. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be disclosed, access was restricted to the researcher. To protect respondents' privacy, it was ensured that only the researcher could access the survey

results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the online survey results to ensure that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to respondents the nature of their participation, the study's purpose and benefits, and the confidentiality of their responses, as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Respondents, without restriction, were able to ask questions about the study. Furthermore, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to any harm. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or otherwise unacceptable statements that would be offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed solely to collect academic information, and participants were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured that respondents had ample time to complete the online survey. The respondents were given the option not to answer questions that caused psychological or emotional distress, and they were free to withdraw from the study if they felt they could not discuss the information requested. The researcher valued their participation and prioritized their welfare throughout the study.

Justice and Transparency To avoid bias in selecting respondents, the researcher treated all individuals as equal, regardless of whether they would be included in the survey. The researcher did not exhibit bias in selecting the study's respondents—anyone who met the criterion of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher ensured respect for respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent on data collection, the researcher provided tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment

of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. On the other hand, to ensure transparency in this study, all communication related to the research was conducted honestly and openly. To safeguard participants' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed for this study. All necessary documents supporting the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the results of the study.

Qualification of the Researcher

The researcher ensured that respondents' responses were not influenced by any other factor, such as a conflict of interest. The study's findings could be accessed by respondents, parents, and school administrators at the participating schools, provided they followed proper protocols to protect respondents' anonymity. The researcher also acknowledged the efforts of everyone who contributed to the study's success. The Division of Davao del Norte was provided with a furnished copy of the research results so that it can be accessed by the respondents and used for learning and further study.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment, using ample, readily available learning materials, and the study was conducted within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the ratings of the respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them, to avoid errors in encoding. Additionally, the analysis and results were rigorous and aligned, which serves as a primary basis for adequacy.

Community Involvement

The researcher emphasized the importance of active community participation at every stage

of the research process. From initial planning through dissemination of findings, community involvement was prioritized to ensure that the research remained relevant and respectful of local contexts and needs. The researcher plans to engage community members, including parents, teachers, and local leaders, by sharing preliminary and final results and by soliciting their insights and feedback. Furthermore, the community was actively involved in crucial research decisions, including establishing priorities, selecting methodologies aligned with local customs and practices, and determining how the findings would be used for community development or educational improvements. This collaborative approach aimed to foster transparency, mutual respect, and empowerment, ensuring that the research outcomes were meaningful and beneficial to the community. Overall, community involvement was integral to the success and integrity of the research, promoting a shared sense of ownership and commitment to positive educational change.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the grade six elementary pupils in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. In this study, 168 respondents were selected using stratified random sampling. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were used to select respondents. The primary consideration of this

study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bonafide grade six pupils in Asuncion Davao del Norte and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.4. Research Instrument—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument was concerned with assertiveness in learning, which was adapted from the study of Waqar and Sanjay (2022), used as an instrument to measure the assertiveness of pupils’ learning, which consists of four domains, namely: passive behavior, aggressive behavior, manipulation, and harmonious assertiveness. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. In responding to the questionnaire, the respondents used a 5-point Likert scale, as follows: 5–Always, 4–Oftentimes, 3–Sometimes Agree, 2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Assertiveness in Learning, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Descriptive Level Interpretation of Assertiveness in Learning

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The assertiveness in learning is always observed.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The assertiveness in learning is oftentimes observed.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The assertiveness in learning is sometimes observed.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The assertiveness in learning is seldom observed.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The assertiveness in learning is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the Academic Attitude of learners, adapted from June and Eamoraphan (2019), and divided into three domains: academic self-concept, enjoyment, and perceived value. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. The questionnaire was pilot tested in a nearby school and obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value greater than 0.700, which ensured that the questionnaires had a high level of internal consistency. The scaling was performed by setting 0.5 of

the value of 5 as the average cutoff point (the fair level), with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administration of the instrument, it was validated by three experts and revised based on their comments. In responding to the questionnaire, the respondents used a 5-point Likert scale, as follows: 5–Always, 4–Oftentimes, 3–Sometimes Agree, 2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Academic Attitude of learners, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Descriptive Level Interpretation of Academic Attitude

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The academic attitude is always manifested.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The academic attitude is often manifested.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The academic attitude is sometimes manifested.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The academic attitude is seldom manifested.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The academic attitude is never manifested.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher proceeded with the study after validating the research questionnaire.

Permission to Conduct the Study The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the Schools Division Superintendent, and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Asuncion, Davao del Norte.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire

The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after obtaining approval to conduct the study. This was done on March 22-24, 2024. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly explained to the study’s identified respondents. To administer the questionnaire, the researcher distributed it in accordance with health protocols. The study participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires. Subsequently, the collected data were subjected to quantitative analysis.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organized the data per indicator. After which, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The researcher employed various statistical tools to analyze the collected data, each serving a specific purpose

in addressing the research objectives. Mean This statistical measure was used to characterize the levels of assertiveness in learn-

ing and academic attitude among pupils. It provided a central value that helped address Objectives 1 and 2 by summarizing the overall tendencies in the dataset.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation This tool was utilized to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between the independent variable (assertiveness in learning) and the dependent variable (academic attitude). It measures the degree of linear association between paired data points, with the correlation coefficient denoted by r . This analysis helped determine whether higher levels of assertiveness are significantly associated with more positive academic attitudes.

Multiple Linear Regression This analysis was conducted to evaluate the extent to which

assertiveness in learning predicts or influences academic attitude. It allowed the researcher to examine the significance and strength of the independent variable's impact on the dependent variable, providing insights into the predictive relationship and potential for targeted interventions to improve academic attitudes through fostering assertiveness. Additionally, the researcher ensured that assumptions such as normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity were checked to validate the appropriateness of these statistical methods. These analyses collectively provided a comprehensive understanding of the relationships and influences between assertiveness and academic attitude among the pupils in Asuncion, Davao del Norte.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results obtained from the collected data. It was sequenced according to the study objectives presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of assertiveness in learning and academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; the significant relationship between assertiveness in learning and academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; and the influence of assertiveness in learning on the academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte.

3.2. *Passive Behavior*—Table 1 shows the summary of assertiveness in learning in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. It shows that the overall mean of assertiveness in learning of assertiveness in learners is 3.35, which is described as moderately extensive. It means that it is sometimes observed. More so, assertiveness in learning of assertiveness in learners in terms of aggressive attitude acquired the highest mean score of 3.48 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while, assertiveness in learning of assertiveness in learners in terms of manipulation acquired the lowest mean score of 3.26 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the

learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The result indicates that learners take responsibility for their learning, seek clarification when needed, and contribute to discussions and activities. This supports Lee et al. (2023), who assert that assertive learners actively engage with the learning materials, ask questions, and seek additional information to enhance their understanding. This level of engagement often leads to a deeper grasp of the subject matter. This supports Nnodum's (2021) idea that assertive learners are more likely to challenge information, think critically, and express their perspectives. This contributes to a rich and diverse learning environment where different viewpoints are considered and discussed.

Table 1. Summary on Assertiveness in Learning of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Passive Attitude	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Aggressive Attitude	3.48	Extensive
Manipulation	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Harmonious Assertiveness	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.35	Moderately Extensive

3.3. *Academic Attitude of Learners*—In Table 2, the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. As shown in the table, learners’ academic attitude obtained an overall mean score of 3.23 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. Adding

more, results on Table 10 show that the academic attitude of learners in terms of academic self-concept acquired the highest mean score of 3.46, described as extensive and interpreted as often manifested. In contrast, learners’ academic attitude in terms of perceived value had the lowest mean score of 3.10, indicating a moderate level of perceived value and interpreted as sometimes manifested.

Table 2. Summary on Academic Attitude of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Academic Self-concept	3.46	Extensive
Enjoyment	3.42	Extensive
Perceived Value	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.23	Moderately Extensive

This implies that the motivation, engagement, work ethic, and overall outlook on learning are sometimes manifested by the learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The result supports Xie et al. (2022)’s idea that students with a moderate academic attitude display balanced motivation. They are motivated to succeed but not overly stressed, allowing for a healthy level of drive to excel in their studies. They engage in learning activities with a level of enthusiasm that is conducive to their academic goals. They actively participate in class, complete assignments, and seek additional resources for understanding. This also supports Agormedah et al., (2021) findings that students

with moderate academic attitudes practice effective time management. They allocate sufficient time for studying, attending classes, and participating in extracurricular activities, allowing for a balanced lifestyle.

3.4. *Relationship Between Assertiveness in Learning and Academic Attitude of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte*—The results of the analysis on the relationship between assertiveness in learning and the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficient was used to assess the relationship between the variables. Table 10

shows that assertiveness in learning has a significant positive relationship with the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte, with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.617, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of assertiveness in learning changes, learners' academic attitudes also change significantly. Adding more, results on the table shows that assertiveness in learning in terms of passive behavior; aggressive behavior; manipulation; and harmonious assertiveness have significant positive relationship with the academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.412, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.516, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.340, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.662, p < 0.05$), respectively. The result implies that assertiveness in learning can significantly improve the academic attitude of learners by fostering a proactive, confident, and engaged approach to the educational process. The findings align with Waqar and Sanjay's (2022) proposition that as-

sertive learners are more likely to actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, and express their opinions. This engagement enhances their understanding of the material and demonstrates a proactive attitude toward learning. Assertiveness involves expressing thoughts and ideas clearly and confidently. Likewise, assertiveness in the educational context refers to students' ability to express their feelings, needs, and views honestly and firmly without harming themselves or others (Yu, W. et.al., 2023). This ability is essential in daily life and in the learning process, as students must interact with classmates and teachers openly and confidently. Hence, assertive learners are better equipped to communicate with peers and instructors, leading to more effective collaboration and a positive academic environment. They are adept at advocating for their own needs. Whether it's seeking clarification on assignments, discussing accommodations, or expressing concerns, assertiveness allows learners to take control of their educational experience.

Table 3. Relationship Between Assertiveness in Learning and Academic Attitude of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Passive Behavior	0.412*	0.000	Reject H_0
Aggressive Behavior	0.516*	0.000	Reject H_0
Manipulation	0.340*	0.001	Reject H_0
Harmonious Assertiveness	0.662*	0.000	Reject H_0
Overall Assertiveness in Learning	0.578*	0.000	Reject H_0

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$.

3.5. *Influence of Assertiveness in Learning on the Academic Attitude of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte*—The significance of the influence of assertiveness in learning on the academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table

11 shows that when assertiveness in learning in terms of passive behavior, aggressive behavior, manipulation, and harmonious assertiveness are considered as predictors of the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte, the model is significant, as evidenced by the F-value of 102.331 with $p < 0.05$.

It is therefore stated that assertiveness in learning predicts learners' academic attitudes in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.444 indicates that assertiveness in learning accounts for 44.40%. According to Waqar Sanjay, (2022), effective classroom management is crucial for maintaining an orderly and conducive learning environment. Teachers who manage their classrooms well set clear rules and expectations, enforce them consistently, and address behavioral issues promptly. This minimizes disruptions and helps maintain a focused learning atmosphere. In addition, the table shows that domains of assertiveness in learning significantly influence learners' academic attitudes in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This table also indicates that assertiveness in learning, in terms of passive and aggressive behaviors, is significant when predictors are considered. This means that the extent of learners' academic attitudes increases by 0.162 and 0.295 for each

unit increase in assertiveness in learning. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of assertiveness in learning significantly influence the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This affirmed that learners' academic attitudes are a function of assertiveness in learning in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. The result corroborates Blegur et al. (2023), who assert that assertive learners are more likely to prioritize their academic responsibilities. They proactively manage their time, set goals, and take the necessary steps to meet deadlines, leading to a more positive and organized academic attitude. A person demonstrates assertive behaviour when they communicate their thoughts, feelings, and rights in a way that does not minimize but instead comprehends and respects those of others in order to preserve positive relationships, settle disputes with others, and keep their own needs from being suppressed or stifled (Morsi Prince, 2021).

Table 4. Influence of Assertiveness in Learning on the Academic Attitude of Learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Assertiveness in Learning	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decision
Passive Behavior	.162*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H_0
Aggressive Behavior	.296*	.408	.047	.000	Reject H_0
Manipulation	.087	.108	.049	.082	Accept H_0
Harmonious Assertiveness	.032	.162	.053	.119	Accept H_0
R^2				0.444	
F-value				102.331*	
p-value				0.000	

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$. R^2 represents the proportion of variance in academic attitude explained by assertiveness in learning.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendations. The discussion was supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domains of assertiveness in learning significantly influence the academic attitude of learners, utilizing

a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 168 Grade 6 learners in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte as respondents using a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Assertiveness in learning of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte got an overall mean of 3.35 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Learners' assertiveness in learning, in terms of passive behavior, aggressive behavior, manipulation, and harmonious assertiveness, yielded mean scores of 3.27, 3.48, 3.26, and 3.39, respectively. The academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.23 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Academic attitude of learners in terms of academic self-concept, enjoyment, and perceived value obtained the mean scores 3.46, 3.42, and 3.10, respectively. Assertiveness in learning has a significant positive relationship with the academic attitude of learners in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .617$, $p < 0.05$). Assertiveness in learning of learners in terms of passive behavior, aggressive behavior, manipulation, and harmonious assertiveness have significant positive relationship with the academic attitude of learners with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.412$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.516$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.340$, $p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.662$, $p < 0.05$). Assertiveness in learning, in terms of passive and aggressive behaviors, significantly influenced learners' academic attitudes in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte, as evidenced by an F-value of 102.331 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.444 indicated that assertiveness in learning has contributed significantly to

the variability of the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte by 44.40% from the total variability.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Assertiveness in learning of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was moderately extensive. Meanwhile, assertiveness in learning of learners in terms of manipulation acquired an extensive descriptive rating, while assertiveness in learning of learners in terms of passive behavior, aggressive behavior, and harmonious assertiveness got moderately extensive descriptive ratings. The result indicates that learners take responsibility for their learning, seek clarification when needed, and contribute to discussions and activities. Academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was rated as moderately extensive. Academic attitude of learners in terms of academic self-concept and enjoyment belong to extensive ratings, while, academic attitude of learners in terms of perceived value got moderately extensive rating. This implies that the motivation, engagement, work ethic, and overall outlook on learning is sometimes manifested by the learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. Assertiveness in learning has a significant positive relationship with the academic attitude of learners in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. This means that as the extent of assertiveness in learning changes, the academic attitude of learners also significantly changes. The result implies that assertiveness in learning can significantly improve learners' academic attitudes by fostering a proactive, confident, and engaged approach to the educational process. Assertiveness in learning, in terms of passive and aggressive behavior, significantly influenced learners' academic attitudes in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This affirmed that learners' academic attitudes are a function of assertiveness in learning in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. Re-

cent research, building on Jakubowski-Spector's foundational work in "The Theory of Assertion," revealed a strong positive relationship between assertiveness and various aspects of academic attitudes and performance. While Jakubowski-Spector's original focus was on establishing the philosophical principles of assertion, such as human rights and their distinction from aggression, subsequent studies have demonstrated that assertiveness among learners is significantly correlated with higher motivation, better academic achievement, and improved performance on school tasks. Assertive students tend to communicate more openly and respectfully, thereby fostering more positive interactions with teachers and peers. Additionally, assertiveness helps reduce anxiety by enabling individuals to express their feelings and needs confidently, thereby promoting a more positive academic attitude. The research also highlights that teachers' assertiveness positively influences students' academic attitudes, underscoring the importance of an assertive educational environment. Overall, Jakubowski-Spector's theoretical framework has underpinned the development of assertiveness training programs that enhance self-esteem, reduce stress, and improve academic outcomes.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education (DepEd) should integrate social-emotional learning programs into the curriculum to explicitly teach assertiveness skills. These programs can enhance students' emotional intelligence, self-awareness, and interpersonal communication. Moreover, DepEd should develop and implement policies that promote a supportive and inclusive school culture. En-

courage policies that prohibit bullying, discrimination, and other behaviors that may hinder learners' development of assertiveness.

School Heads Should foster a positive and inclusive school climate where students feel comfortable expressing themselves. Implement anti-bullying initiatives and promote a culture of respect and open communication. They should offer professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their skills in fostering assertiveness in the classroom. Create a learning environment that encourages collaboration and the sharing of best practices among educators.

Teachers Should integrate activities and discussions on assertiveness within lesson plans. Provide opportunities for students to practice assertiveness skills through group work, presentations, and class discussions. They should also recognize and address individual student needs. Provide additional support and guidance to students who may struggle with assertiveness, fostering a personalized approach to their development.

Learners Should engage in self-reflection to understand personal communication styles and areas for improvement. Recognize the importance of assertiveness in learning and its positive impact on academic attitude. They should also actively participate in classroom activities, discussions, and group projects. Seek opportunities to express thoughts, ask questions, and engage with peers and instructors.

Future Researchers Investigate the influence of cultural and diversity factors on assertiveness in learning. Explore how cultural backgrounds may shape assertiveness styles and effectiveness in different educational contexts.

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